

Carbon Dioxide Capturing using Activated Carbon Produced from Orange Peels

Okore, Chioma C.^{1*}, Ugenyi, Assumpta U.², Ogbuka, Ifeanyi B.³, Ajoku, Uzoma J.⁴,
Onyechere, Uju C.⁵, Arimanwa, Ijeoma C.⁶, Irechukwu, Obianuju E.⁷ and Okoye, Juliet C.⁸

¹³⁴⁵⁶⁷⁸Department of Environmental Biology, Federal Polytechnic Nekede, Owerri, Imo-State

²Department of Environmental Management and Toxicology

University of Agriculture and Environmental Science, Umuagwo, Imo State

Corresponding Author: chiemeziechioma@gmail.com 08037642354

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Abstract

This study determined the effectiveness of utilizing activated carbon produced from orange peel wastes (A.COP) for CO₂ capture, which contributes to climate change. Orange peels were washed under tap water, oven-dried at 80°C for two days, ground using an electric grinder, placed in a crucible, and carbonized in a laboratory muffle furnace at 400–450°C for one hour. Carbon was cooled in desiccator, soaked in 0.1M NaOH, 24hours, filtered, washed severally with distilled water using a muslin cloth. The residue was oven-dried at 105°C to a constant weight. Generator was started, CO₂ of environment (control), was recorded using digital CO₂ monitor, for total of 15mins, at 5mins intervals (triplicate). Improvised metal cylinder, same diameter (5cm) of generator exhaust was made, one end was fixed metal wire gauze with screw and clip. CO₂ of generator exhaust without A.COP was recorded. 5g of A.COP was poured in from open end, covered with metallic gauze, fixed up with clip and screwed to exhaust end of generator. CO₂ from free end of generator exhaust was recorded. Characterization of A.COP was carried out viz moisture content, ash content, bulk density and particle size. Results recorded CO₂ of environment at time of study (563, 568, 600, average 577ppm); CO₂ of generator exhaust before loading A.COP (1400, 1389, 1392, average 1394ppm); CO₂ of A.COP (746, 747 749, average 747.3ppm). Average CO₂ captured with 5 g A.COP is 129.3ppm. CO₂ reduced with A.COP from 1394ppm to 747.3ppm. This revealed a 46.39% reduction in CO₂ emitted. A.COP was effective in capturing CO₂. Orange peels should be used as alternative for producing activated carbon.

Key words: Activated carbon, CO₂ capture, generator exhaust fumes, orange peels

INTRODUCTION

Global warming has taken on a much more worrying dimension due to the continuous increase in greenhouse gases (GHGs) emissions. Man-made CO₂ is one of the major contributors to global warming as a result of the staggering amounts that are being released into the atmosphere on a daily basis (Leung *et al.*, 2014). In the past decades, considerable effort has been put into developing new technologies to reduce excessive CO₂ emission and mitigate its long-term effects

on climate change. The main treatment technologies used to capture CO₂ from flue gas streams are absorption, adsorption and membrane separation. Generally, liquid-phase absorption is the most commonly used method for CO₂ capture because of its higher efficiency. However, this process presents several drawbacks, such as high energy consumption and serious concerns related to solvents use and waste management.

Hence, adsorption emerges as a promising contender technology, as it allows achieving high CO₂ uptake capacities while maintaining high thermal stability, which is a prerequisite for operating under high-temperature conditions such as those involved in post-combustion power plants. Another major advantage offered by the adsorption is the possibility to restore the initial performance of the used solid adsorbent through regeneration by electrical swing adsorption (ESA) or pressure swing adsorption (PSA) and thermal swing adsorption (TSA) processes. These adsorption facilities make use of appropriate porous materials such as activated carbons, zeolites and metal-organic frameworks regarding their large surface area per unit of mass as well as suitable pore size distribution. In general, activated carbons are preferentially used considering their relatively low cost and availability, especially when obtained from low-cost biomass/waste precursors.

A key requirement for designing solid adsorption process systems for carbon capture is the choice of a suitable sorbent with desirable properties in terms of low cost, high CO₂ selectivity and adsorption capacity, fast kinetics, insensitivity to moisture and other feed impurities, cyclical stability and ease of regeneration (Chen *et al.*, 2009). Carbon materials are highly attractive for CO₂ capture because they do not require moisture removal; present a high CO₂ capture capacity at ambient pressures; are easy to regenerate and are mechanically and chemically stable, unlike most zeolites and some metal organic frameworks (MOFs).

Activated carbon materials are amorphous porous forms of carbon often obtained as a residue after the volatile components of the source- carbonaceous material are eliminated by the thermal pyrolytic process occurring in the absence of oxygen. Note that appropriate carbonization temperature is needed in order to avoid char yield decrease through further decomposition and release of gaseous and condensable products. Subsequent activation step permits the development of porosity through the diffusion of activating agent into the charcoal. This step depend on several parameters such as the ratio char/reactant, the temperature and chemical nature of the activating agent, which allows obtaining microporous activated carbon with larger surface area and narrow pore size that can be appropriate candidate for CO₂ capture at ambient temperature and pressure. Activated carbons have been promoted as a low-cost adsorbent with high adsorption capacity for organic and non-organic pollutant removal (Bhatnagar *et al.*, 2013). Activated carbons also show good stability when operated under moist environments due to their hydrophobic character, and can be readily regenerated thermally or by evacuation with lower energy requirements. Activated carbons have mainly been used as adsorbents or catalysts, and they have several applications in gas purification, waste-water treatment, filtration, soil remediation and related environmental processes.

Activated carbon is produced via physical and chemical activation. Activated carbon production by physical activation is a two- step procedure which involves thermal decomposition and physical modification of the source material in a pyrolysis furnace process at high temperatures (500–1000°C) and under inert atmosphere, followed by thermal activation in the presence of an oxidizing gas such as steam or carbon dioxide. For chemical activation, the same procedures are carried, and activation is completed after the source material has been impregnated with a

dehydrating agent such as sulfuric acid, potassium hydroxide, zinc chloride, sodium hydroxide, etc. The resulting activated carbon product often possesses a large surface area per unit volume with multi-channel pores which aid adsorption.

The potentials of the porous activated carbon adsorbent can be further improved by surface chemistry modification via a variety of techniques: chemical, biological, physical, oxidative and non oxidative.

Surface area and pore volume are used for liquid and gas separation, medicine, and catalyst while total surface area may support the accessibility of active site relating to the catalytic activity. Pore size of the activated carbon can be separated into the micropores ($d \leq 2\text{nm}$), mesopores ($d = 2$ to 50 nm) and macropores ($d \geq 50\text{ nm}$) which are needed to improve the transport process of particles or molecules inside porous networks and facilitate the adsorption of larger molecules.

Activated carbons are known for their useful properties such as chemical and thermal stability, wide abundance, and ease of synthesis (Haimour *et al.*, 2006). As with most adsorbents, adsorption capacity of activated carbons depends primarily on the preparation methods and initial structural properties of starting materials. The primary source material used for synthesis of activated carbons is any organic material with a high carbon content.

Carbon dioxide gas emitted from the use of generators due to poor electricity distribution is one of the main causes of global warming and ocean acidification. In order to reduce the concentration of atmospheric CO_2 , much research has been focused on the development of new technologies for CO_2 capture. Currently, absorption, at the industrial level, using amine solutions is the technology that is more studied (Deguchi *et al.*, 2011) and it's commercially used for CO_2 capture in power plants. The major drawback in using amine solutions are, high energy consumption, degradation and vaporization of solvent and corrosion of process equipment (Shafeeyan *et al.*, 2010). Adsorbents such as silica, metal oxides, metal organic frame works (MOFs), zeolites and activated carbon (AC) have been tested for CO_2 capture (Kim *et al.*, 2010; Choi *et al.*, 2009). Though some of these adsorbents perform well in CO_2 capture but they are costly and require multi-step fabrication procedures, high regeneration temperature and undergo significant loss of adsorption capacity after several cycles (Servilla and Fuertes, 2011). For this reason, research interest for the production of activated carbons from agricultural and industrial wastes becomes a necessity.

The control of anthropogenic CO_2 emission is a crucial matter due to assertion that CO_2 gas contributes hugely to global climate change, the knowledge of this research will give insight on how to manage CO_2 emission in generators. The biomass wastes are the most common materials studied for this purpose, since they are renewable, usually available in large quantities and cheaper than other materials. The use of fruit wastes in the production of activated carbon will reduce cost of production.

METHODOLOGY

Collection and Preparation of Sample

The orange peels wastes were collected from Industrial Cluster Market, Owerri, Imo State. It was screened and washed thoroughly under tap water to remove all dirt and after, it was dried in an oven at 80°C for 2 days. The orange peels was ground to fine powder and ready for carbonization.

Carbonization

The dried grounded samples were put in crucible and then carbonized in a lab tech muffle furnace set at (400-450)°C for 1 hour. It was brought out and cooled in a desiccator and stored for activation.

Preparation of Activated Carbon using Chemical Method

The carbonized samples were poured in beaker and soaked with 0.1 molar NaOH for 24 hours. After soaking, the samples were filtered, washed severally with distilled water using a muslin cloth. The residue was oven dried at 105°C to constant wet.

CO₂ Capturing

An improvised metal cylinder, with the same diameter of a generator exhaust, was made (5 cm). The one end was fixed a metal wire gauze with screw and clip. From the open end, 5 g of Activated Carbon was poured into the improvised cylinder and then covered with metallic gauze and fixed up with clip and screw to the exhaust end of the generator. The generator was started and the CO₂ was monitored for a maximum period of 15 minute, but at 5 minutes intervals the CO₂ from the free end of the generator exhaust was recorded using digital CO₂ monitor. The CO₂ of the generator exhaust without activated carbon was recorded, also the CO₂ of the environment was monitored and noted to serve as controls (Fig. 1).

Fig 1: CO₂ Capturing setup

CHARACTERIZATION OF ACTIVATED CARBON

Moisture Content

The moisture content of the samples was determined by the following method:

Ten (10 g) of the material was weighed in a moisture can placed in an electric oven and dried at 105°C for about 4 hours. It was cooled in a dessicator and weighed at ½ hour interval until the differences between two consecutive weighing is not less than 0.005 g (ASTM, 2006).

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ Moisture Content} = 100 \frac{(M - M_1)}{M}$$

M

Where M is Mass in gram of the material taken for test

M₁ is Mass in gram of the material after drying

Ash Content

Two (2 g) of the activated carbon with no moisture content was weighed into a crucible. The crucible was placed in an electric oven at 110-120°C for about 4 hours. Thereafter the crucible was removed in the oven and placed in a muffle furnace and incinerated for about 5 hours at 550°C in a muffle furnace. The sample was cooled and kept in a dessicator and then later weighed. The increase in weight of the crucible is as a result of the ash content (ASTM, 2006).

Calculation:

Ash content on Air dry basis

$$\% \text{ Moisture Content} = 10,000 \frac{M_1}{M} (100 - X)$$

M

Where M_1 is Mass in gram of the ash

M is Mass in gram of the material taken for the test sample.

X is % moisture content present in the material taken for the test

Particle Size

The following sieves were used for particle size distribution:

$\geq 2000 \mu\text{m}$, $1000 \mu\text{m}$, $500 \mu\text{m}$, $250 \mu\text{m}$ and $\leq 150 \mu\text{m}$

Procedure:

The sieves were properly cleaned before and were placed in order of their sizes. Then hundred (100) g of the sample was weighed and introduced into the upper sieved i.e $2000 \mu\text{m}$ whereas the lowest sieve $150 \mu\text{m}$ is the one carrying the receiver. The sieves were placed on a mechanical shaker and ran for about 10 mins. The sieves were removed and the content of each sieves were carefully gathered and weighed i.e each material collected from each seive was weighed (ASTM, 2006).

Calculation:

Material retained on any given sieve in %

= Mass in gram of the material retained in the given size.

Note: The sum of the % of the material retained in each sieve should sum up to 100.

Bulk Density

The bulk density of the activated carbon was determined by measuring 1 g of each activated carbon into a 10 ml graduated measuring cylinder. The sample in the cylinder was tapped severally and the volume of the sample noted. The ratio of the mass / volume is regarded as the bulk density of each sample (ASTM, 2006).

Bulk density = Mass

Volume

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

CO₂ capture

Table 1 shows the result of CO₂ capture of the environment at the time of this study, measured every 5 minutes interval for a total period of 15 minutes, as 563 ppm, 568 ppm and 600 ppm while

calculated average is 577 ppm. CO₂ capture of generator exhaust **without** activated carbon from orange peels is 1400 ppm, 1389 ppm, 1392 ppm, while calculated average is 1394 ppm. CO₂ capture of generator exhaust with activated carbon from orange peels is 746 ppm, 747 ppm, 749 ppm, while calculated average is 747.3 ppm. The calculated CO₂ captured with 5 g orange peels is 129.34 ppm.

Table 1: CO₂ capture values

Time interval	CO ₂ capture of the environment (ppm) at the time of the study	CO ₂ capture of generator exhaust without activated carbon from orange peels (ppm)	CO ₂ capture of generator exhaust with activated carbon from orange peels (ppm)
5 mins	563	1400	746
5 mins	568	1389	747
5 mins	600	1392	749
Calculated Average	577 ppm	1394 ppm	747.3 ppm

- CO₂ captured by orange peels

$$= \frac{\text{Average CO}_2 \text{ of generator exhaust} - \text{Average CO}_2 \text{ captured}}{\text{Mass of Activated carbon}}$$

$$= \frac{1394 \text{ ppm} - 747.3 \text{ ppm}}{5 \text{ g}}$$

$$= 129.34 \text{ ppm}$$

$$\% \text{ CO}_2 \text{ reduction} = \frac{\text{Initial CO}_2 \text{ capture} - \text{Final CO}_2 \text{ capture}}{\text{Initial CO}_2 \text{ capture}} \times 100\%$$

$$= \frac{1394 \text{ ppm} - 747.3 \text{ ppm}}{1394 \text{ ppm}} \times 100\%$$

$$= 46.39\%$$

$$= 46.39\%$$

CHARACTERIZATION OF ACTIVATED CARBON OF ORANGE PEELS

Table 2 shows the results of the physicochemical parameters of the activated carbon from the orange peels wastes. The % moisture content is 13.335 whereas the % ash content is 21.111. The bulk density is 0.543 g/cm³.

Table 3 shows the result of particle size of the activated carbon produced from the orange peels measured with different sizes of the sieves viz $\geq 2000\mu\text{m}$, 1000 μm , 500 μm , 250 μm , 150 μm and $\leq 150 \mu\text{m}$.

Table 2: Physicochemical parameters of the activated carbon from the orange peels wastes

Parameter	Values
% moisture content	13.335
% Ash content	21.111

Table 3: Particle sizes of activated carbon produced from orange peels

% particle size distribution (μm) using different sieve size (μm)						
Sieve size	≥ 2000	1000	500	250	150	≤ 150
Orange peels	0	2.90	33.30	23.91	18.72	21.18

DISCUSSION

The outcome of this study showed that 5 g of activated carbon produced from orange peel was able to capture 129.34 ppm of carbon dioxide (CO₂) within fifteen minutes at five minutes intervals of the analysis. The result shows that emitted CO₂ reduced when activated carbon was used as adsorbent from 1394 ppm to 747.3 ppm. This revealed a 46.39% reduction in CO₂ emitted. Recently, many authors have used biomass for preparing activated carbons of high porosity useful for high capacity CO adsorption (up to 7.0 mmol/g at 273K), depending on the carbon precursors and the preparation methods (Li *et al.*, 2019).

According to Inam *et al.*, (2020) reduced percentage ash and moisture contents of activated carbon indicate good adsorption characteristics. They recorded 18.18% and 3.0% of ash and moisture contents respectively while in this study we recorded 21.111% and 13.335% respectively which is in line with their finding. Jose Aurelio Sosa *et al.*, (2023) also recorded % moisture of 9.2 and % ash content of 3.09 for orange peels activated carbon.. They equally noted particle size of 0.4 mm of orange peels activated carbon. According to Ketabchi *et al.*, (2023) carbonization and activation temperature could play a critical role in the nature of the activated carbon produced, for the removal of adsorbates; in this study the carbonization temperature and time respectively are 400-450°C and 1hour which was chemically activated in 0.1M NaOH for 24 hours, and oven dried at 105°C to constant weight. These conditions enabled the 46.39% reduction in CO₂ emitted.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The outcome of this study proved that orange peels were effective in the capturing of carbon dioxide within the duration of this study. This implies that converting waste of orange peels into useful materials such as activated carbon can help to manage the CO₂ emissions that contribute to global warming.

Recommendations

It is recommended based on the findings that:

1. Orange peels wastes should be use in the production of activated carbon for use as adsorbents in generators to manage carbon dioxide emissions.
2. Industrial manufacturers should include devices in generators, that will hold activated carbon adsorbents to manage CO₂ emissions.
3. Adequate and optimized modification is highly recommended to avoid pore blockage affecting adsorption of CO₂.

REFERENCES

- Bhatnagar, A. (2013). An overview of the modification methods of activated carbon for its water treatment applications *Chem. Eng. J.* **1**:11-23.
- Chen, B., Al-Mamoori, A., Krishnamurthy, A., Rownaghi, A.A. & Rezaei, F. (2009). Sorption of naphthalene and 1-naphthol by biochars of orange peels with different pyrolytic temperatures. *Chemosphere*, **5**, 834–849.
- Choi, S., Drese, J. & Jones, C.W. (2009). Adsorbent materials for carbon dioxide capture from large anthropogenic point sources. *Chem. Sus.*, **2**(7), 96-854.
- Deguchi, G., Chen, C.H., Shimon, D., Lee, J.J., Mentink-Vigier, F., Hung, I., Sievers, C., Jones, C.W. & Hayes, S.E. (2011). The missing bicarbonate in CO₂ chemisorption reactions on solid amine sorbents. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **140** (28), 8648–8651.
- Haimour, N., Atlaskin, A.A., Kryuchkov, S.S. & Yanbikov, N.R. (2006). Utilization of date stones for production of activated carbon using phosphoric acid. *Waste Manage*, **239**, 116-578.
- Inam, E.J., Edet, J.B., Akpan, P.E., Ite, K.E. (2020). Characterization and equilibrium studied for the removal of methylene blue from aqueous solution using activated bone char. *Journal of Materials and Environmental Science*, **1**(10), 1667-1675 ISSN:2028-2508
- Ketabchi, M.R., Babamohammadi, S., Davies, W.G., Gorbounov, M., Soltani, S.M. (2023). Latest advances and challenges in carbon capture using bio-based sorbents: A state of the art review. *Elsevier. Carbon Capture Science & Technology*, **6**(2023) 100087
- Kim, H., Kim, Y., Yoon, M., Lim, S., Park, S. M., Seo, G. & Kim, K. (2010). Highly selective carbon dioxide sorption in an organic molecular porous material. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **132**(2010) 12200 -12202
- Rao, A.B., Akhtar, F., Keshavarzi, N., Shakarova, D. & Cheung, O. (2006). Evaluation of potential cost reductions from improved amine-based CO capture systems. *Energy Policy*, **4**, 55877–55883.
- Servilla, G. & Fuertes, S. (2011). Post-combustion CO₂ capture technology development. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, **127**: 17998–17999.
- Sayari, A., Aki, S.N., Mellein, B.R. & Saurer, E.M. (2011). Flue gas treatment via CO adsorption. *Chem. Eng. J.* **1**, 7-8.
- Shafeeyan, M.S., Daud, W.M., Houshm, A. & Shamiri, A. (2010). A review on surface modification of activated carbon for carbon dioxide adsorption., *Journal of Analytical & Applied Pyrolysis*, **89**:143-151.
- Sosa, A.J., Laines, J.R., Garcia, D.S., Hernandez, R., Zappi, M., Espinosa de los Monteros, A.E. (2023). Activated carbon: A review of residual precursors, synthesis processes, characterization techniques, and applications in the improvement of biogas. *Environ. Eng. Res.* **28**(3), 220100. <https://doi.org/10.4491/eer.2022.100>